

Studies on Some Beryllium Complexes of Aromatic Schiff Bases†

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Manuscript received 19 September 1978, revised 9 February 1980, accepted 31 March 1980

Bis(N-salicylaldiminato)beryllium(II), *bis(salicylaldoximinato)beryllium(II)*, *bis(N-o-hydroxyphenylsalicylaldiminato)beryllium(II)*, *mono(N-o-carboxyphenylsalicylaldiminato)beryllium(II)dihydrate* and *bis(N-p-aryl salicylaldiminato)beryllium(II)* (where *p-aryl* = *p-tolyl*, *p-anisyl*, *p-chlorophenyl* and *p-nitrophenyl*) are isolated and characterised by their elemental analysis, ir and pmr spectral studies. The ir spectra of the ligands show a broad, weak to medium intensity band around 2700 cm^{-1} attributable to intramolecularly bonded OH. The ir spectra of *bis(N-salicylaldiminato)beryllium(II)*, *bis(N-salicylaldoximinato)beryllium(II)* and *bis(N-o-hydroxyphenylsalicylaldiminato)beryllium(II)* show the presence of intermolecularly bonded NH and OH groups. Such findings are further substantiated by the pmr and mass spectral studies.

SCHIFF bases derived from the reaction of salicylaldehyde with primary aromatic amines represent a versatile series of ligands and the metal chelates of these ligands have attracted much attention¹⁻³. The live interest in the Schiff bases and their metal chelates is undoubtedly due to the structural diversity of the complexes, the impracticability of applying normal coordinate methods to the assignment problem and the complexity of the spectra resulting from the presence of phenyl vibrations.

Even though quite a few papers are concerned with the studies on bidentate, tridentate and tetradentate N-alkyl or N-aryl salicylaldimines and their metal chelates with transition and non-transition metals⁴⁻²², very meagre work on beryllium complexes of such ligands has been reported. The limited number of beryllium complexes of Schiff bases studied so far are mostly derived from N-alkyl salicylaldimine and N,N'-ethylene *bis(salicylaldimine)*²³⁻²⁶ or similar Schiff bases using long chain alkyl amines.

The work presented here deals with the syntheses of some new beryllium complexes of bidentate and tridentate N-aryl salicylaldimines and their ir and pmr spectral studies of these complexes.

Experimental

Materials and Methods :

Salicylaldehyde (Sarabhai Merck, LR grade) was distilled under reduced pressure. Aniline derivatives were purified by recrystallisation from alcohol. Aniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine, *p*-chloroaniline,

p-nitroaniline, *o*-aminophenol and anthranilic acid were of C.P. grade. Salicylaldoxime and beryllium nitrate, $\text{Be}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, were of AR grade. The beryllium content was determined by standard method²⁷.

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, Model 221. The pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian Associate, Model T-60 spectrometer operating at 60 Mc/s with TMS as an internal standard. The mass spectra were recorded on CEC 21-110B (USA) double focussing mass spectrometer at a voltage of 70 eV.

Preparation of ligands and their beryllium chelates :

N-aryl salicylaldimines were prepared according to reported methods^{7,11,28,29}. Although N-salicylaldimine could not be isolated in solid state by the reported method¹¹, its beryllium chelate could be prepared by reacting *bis(salicylaldehydato)beryllium(II)* with ammonia *in situ*. All other beryllium chelates reported here were prepared by the following procedure :

N-*p*-tolylsalicylaldimine (0.02 moles) was dissolved in methanol or ethanol (50 ml) and to the clear solution, an aqueous alcoholic beryllium nitrate solution (0.01 mole) in 10 ml was added. The resulting clear yellow solution was refluxed for about an hour on water bath, the pH of the solution was adjusted to ~7 with dilute ammonia (1 : 1) and it was further refluxed. The precipitated yellow solid was filtered on cooling, washed with cold alcohol till free of unreacted ligand, and air or vacuum dried. Mono(N-*o*-carboxyphenyl-salicylaldiminato)beryllium(II) dihydrate was prepared in a similar manner.

† NCL Communication No. 2310.

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TABLE I—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES OF N-ARYL SALICYLALDIMINES AND THEIR BERYLLIUM CHELATES

No.	Name	m.p. °C	C	H	N	Be%
1.	N-phenylsalicylaldimine C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO	51	79.15 (78.63)	5.62 (5.78)	7.10 (7.24)	—
2.	Bis(N-phenylsalicylaldiminato)-beryllium(II) Be(C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NO) ₂	—	78.17 (77.81)	5.58 (4.99)	7.19 (6.98)	2.18 (2.25)
3.	N- <i>p</i> -tolylsalicylaldimine C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO	97	78.96 (79.22)	6.38 (6.65)	6.19 (6.60)	—
4.	Bis(N- <i>p</i> -tolylsalicylaldiminato)-beryllium(II) Be(C ₁₄ H ₁₂ NO) ₂	242	79.56 (77.93)	6.02 (6.07)	6.57 (6.49)	2.18 (2.09)
5.	N- <i>p</i> -anisylsalicylaldimine C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂	89	73.63 (73.66)	6.02 (6.18)	6.23 (6.14)	—
6.	Bis(N- <i>p</i> -anisylsalicylaldiminato)-beryllium(II) Be(C ₁₄ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	118	73.77 (72.81)	5.60 (5.21)	5.92 (6.07)	2.03 (1.95)
7.	N- <i>p</i> -chlorophenylsalicylaldimine C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NOCl	110	67.19 (67.39)	4.67 (4.35)	6.00 (6.05)	—
8.	Bis(N- <i>p</i> -chlorophenylsalicylaldiminato)-beryllium(II) Be(C ₁₃ H ₉ NOCl) ₂	260	66.97 (66.38)	4.11 (3.86)	5.93 (5.96)	1.88 (1.92)
9.	N- <i>p</i> -nitrophenylsalicylaldimine C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃	163-64	64.42 (64.46)	4.41 (4.16)	11.03 (11.57)	—
10.	Bis(N- <i>p</i> -nitrophenylsalicylaldiminato)beryllium(II) Be(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₂ O ₃) ₂	320	62.69 (63.54)	4.61 (3.69)	12.52 (11.40)	1.68 (1.83)
11.	N- <i>o</i> -hydroxyphenylsalicylaldimine C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO ₂	194	72.17 (73.22)	5.40 (5.20)	6.53 (6.57)	—
12.	Bis(N- <i>o</i> -hydroxyphenylsalicylaldiminato)beryllium(II) Be(C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NO ₂) ₂	203-5	71.50 (72.06)	4.80 (4.62)	6.72 (6.47)	2.01 (2.03)
13.	N- <i>o</i> -carboxyphenylsalicylaldimine C ₁₄ H ₁₁ NO ₃	212	69.21 (69.70)	4.50 (4.60)	5.97 (5.81)	—
14.	Mono(N- <i>o</i> -carboxyphenylsalicylaldiminato)beryllium(II) dihydrate Be(C ₁₄ H ₉ NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	>350	60.15 (59.15)	5.12 (4.58)	4.55 (4.93)	3.13 (3.17)
15.	Bis(salicylaldoximinato)beryllium(II) Be(C ₇ H ₆ NO ₂) ₂	298	60.31 (59.78)	4.93 (4.27)	10.50 (9.96)	3.15 (3.21)
16.	Bis(N-salicylaldiminato)-beryllium(II) Be(C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂	250	67.76 (67.46)	5.03 (4.82)	10.78 (11.25)	3.53 (3.62)

Calculated values are given in the parenthesis.

Beryllium chelates of N-phenyl, N-*p*-anisyl, N-*o*-hydroxyphenylsalicylaldimine and salicylaldoxime were prepared by a modified method. Instead of using preformed ligands, the starting reactants were mixed in required amounts in alcohol using freshly prepared beryllium hydroxide and the mixture was refluxed on water bath till all the hydroxide disappeared. The solution was concentrated and cooled and the solid obtained was filtered, washed free of unreacted ligands with small volumes of cold alcohol and air or vacuum dried.

In the preparation of beryllium chelates of N-*p*-chlorophenylsalicylaldimine and N-*p*-nitrophenylsalicylaldimine, the preformed ligand (0.02 mole) was dissolved in a few ml of acetic acid (2-5 ml) and then diluted with aqueous alcohol. The clear solution of the ligand was then reacted with an aqueous solution of beryllium nitrate (0.01 mole, in 10-15 ml H₂O). The pH of the clear solution was adjusted to ~7 with dilute ammonia solution (1 : 1) and the resulting voluminous precipitate was digested on water bath for about 1 hour. The crystalline, yellow precipitate was filtered while hot, washed with alcohol till free of unreacted ligand and air or vacuum dried.

Most of the beryllium chelates were insoluble or sparingly soluble in common organic solvents. The elemental analyses, m.p. are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Although three and two coordinated beryllium compounds are known under special conditions, beryllium prefers usually four coordination³⁰.

The Schiff bases studied here are found to form tetrahedral 1 : 2 metal-ligand complexes with beryllium. These compounds are yellow in colour and have high melting points, a few of them melt with decomposition. The solubility of these complexes in common organic solvents is quite low as expected, but most of them dissolve in DMSO to an appreciable extent which was used to study their pmr spectra.

The probable structure of the beryllium chelates and the ligand are given below :

(A)

(B)

R = (I) H, (II) OH, (III) *p*-C₆H₄CH₃,
(IV) *p*-C₆H₄OCH₃, (V) *p*-C₆H₄Cl,
(VI) *p*-C₆H₄NO₂, (VII) *o*-C₆H₄OH
(VIII) *o*-C₆H₄COOH.

In the ligands an intramolecular hydrogen bond is formed resulting in a stable six-membered ring, since no absorption bands due to free O-H stretching vibration are found in the expected region; instead a broad and weak band is found in the region around 2700 cm^{-1} as reported by Baker and Shulgin³¹ and others^{32,33}. This band disappears in the spectra of all the beryllium complexes which confirms the above assignment and indicates chelate formation. In the infrared spectrum of salicylaldoxime, two bands at 3365 cm^{-1} and 3000 cm^{-1} are assigned to the intermolecularly and intramolecularly bonded OH stretching vibrations respectively³⁴. Sen and coworkers³⁵ have assigned the three bands found at 3600 cm^{-1} , 3445 cm^{-1} and 3230 cm^{-1} in the CCl_4 solution spectrum of the compound to free, intermolecularly and intramolecularly bonded OH stretching vibrations respectively. The spectrum of *bis*(salicylaldoximinato)beryllium(II) shows a broad band at $\sim 2750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is due to intermolecularly bonded OH groups as shown below:

The spectrum of *N*-*o*-hydroxyphenylsalicylaldimine (HCB/Nujol mull, Fig. 1) shows two broad and weak bands at 2500 cm^{-1} and 1850 cm^{-1} which may be due to a double minimum potential hydrogen bond³⁶ of the intramolecularly bonded

Fig. 1. Infrared Spectra of
 — *N*-*o*-Hydroxyphenylsalicylaldimine in HCB/Nujol Mull
 ... *Bis*(*N*-*o*-Hydroxyphenylsalicylaldiminato) Beryllium(II) in Nujol Mull
 —.— *N*-*o*-Hydroxyphenylsalicylaldimine in CCl_4 Solution (0.01M)

phenolic OH. The band due to amine OH group is not observed separately. The CCl_4 solution spectrum of this ligand (Fig. 1) shows a strong band at 3540 cm^{-1} , associated with a weak band at 3590 cm^{-1} and a second broad, medium intensity

band at around 3000 cm^{-1} . The sharp strong band at 3540 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the O-H... π interaction and the associated weak band at 3590 cm^{-1} to free OH stretching vibrations. The lower frequency band at $\sim 3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to phenolic OH intramolecularly bonded to the nitrogen atom of the azomethine group. Such findings are reported by Baker and Shulgin³¹ and they have assigned bands at 3546 cm^{-1} and 2730 cm^{-1} to O-H... π and OH...N intramolecular bonds respectively as shown in the figure for *N*-*o*-hydroxyphenylsalicylaldimine.

The existence of OH π bonds have also been reported by Oki and Iwamura³⁷. Very recently, Malek and Alyea¹⁵ have studied *N*-*o*-hydroxyphenylsalicylaldimine in halocarbon mull and DMSO and assigned the bands in the region $3500\text{-}2900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to OH stretching vibration. These authors have assigned a band near 3500 cm^{-1} to phenolic OH bonded to nitrogen and the band at $\sim 2900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to amine OH bonded to π electrons. This appears to be contradictory to Baker and Shulgin³¹ and our findings. The infrared spectrum of all other *N*-aryl salicylaldimines containing only phenolic OH group have shown only one broad and weak band at $\sim 2700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is due to intramolecular bonding of OH to nitrogen. It is clear from above data that the π -bonded hydrogen bond exists as weak band and appears near 3600 cm^{-1} showing a little shift from free OH region. The similarity of *N*-*o*-hydroxyphenylsalicylaldimine and *N*-salicylaldimine to salicylaldoxime led us to expect intermolecularly bonded O-H or N-H groups in the beryllium complexes of these ligands. It is interesting to observe a broad medium intensity band at 3110 cm^{-1} in the case of *bis*(*N*-*o*-hydroxyphenylsalicylaldiminato)beryllium(II) (Fig. 1) and two medium bands in *bis*(salicylaldiminato)beryllium(II) attributed to intermolecularly bonded OH and N-H groups respectively.

Assignment of characteristic $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$, $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ bands in the region of $1700\text{-}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is difficult due to extensive vibrational coupling and the complexity of the spectra resulting from the presence of phenyl vibrations and the two different metal-ligand bonds (M-O and M-N). In a non-conjugated system C=N normally appears in the $1690\text{-}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region; conjugation shifts it to lower frequency and it is usually found at $\sim 1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the Schiff bases¹². However, the reported ir spectra are generally restricted to the assignments of C=N, C=C and C-O bands^{12,13}. Very recently ir study on ¹⁵N-labelling has been reported^{12,22}, on the aryl Schiff bases in order to ascertain the C=N,

C=C and C-O bands in these ligands and their metal chelates. Percy and Thornton²² have found two ¹⁵N-sensitive bands near 1600 cm⁻¹ and 1570 cm⁻¹ to occur in the spectra of N-aryl salicylaldimines. It was the higher frequency band that has been empirically assigned so far¹² to the ν C=N. The lower frequency band that exhibits a greater ¹⁵N-induced shift is found to be more vibrationally pure. Considering the above facts, these workers have assigned bands at 1627 cm⁻¹ and 1579 cm⁻¹ in N-*p*-anisylsalicylaldimine, 1625 cm⁻¹ and 1579 cm⁻¹ in N-phenylsalicylaldimine and 1613 cm⁻¹ and 1573 cm⁻¹ band in N-*p*-chlorophenylsalicylaldimine to C=N frequency. Further, it was observed that the band at ~1600 cm⁻¹ shifts a little to lower frequency but the band at 1570 cm⁻¹ shows considerable lowering (20-30 cm⁻¹) on complex formation. In the beryllium complexes, we have found that these bands show shifts as reported and therefore can be assigned to C=N stretching vibration.

The 1600 cm⁻¹ ν C=N band occurs at higher frequency when electron donating groups such as CH₃, OCH₃, OH are attached to ortho or para position in the aniline ring and at lower frequency when electron withdrawing groups such as chloro or nitro are attached at para position in the aniline ring. The second ν C=N band is found between 1570-1565 in all these ligands except in N-*o*-hydroxyphenylsalicylaldimine and salicylaldoxime where it occurs at 1585 cm⁻¹ and 1570 cm⁻¹ respectively^{8,4}. The bands appearing in the region of 1500-1300 cm⁻¹ in the ligands as well as in beryllium chelates are due to aromatic CH and =CH vibrations¹⁰. The characteristic strong band at 1280 cm⁻¹ which is present in all the aromatic salicylaldimines is assigned to phenolic ν C-O + δ OH stretching vibrations¹⁰. This band on complex formation with beryllium disappears and a new band is found in the region of 1300-1325 cm⁻¹ which is due to bonded phenolic ν C-O vibration. Another strong band at 1185-1190 cm⁻¹ present in ligands as well as beryllium chelates may be assigned to aryl carbon-nitrogen stretching vibrations^{9,9}. This band does not show any change even when a substituent is introduced in the *p*-position of aniline ring. The strong band at 1140 cm⁻¹ present both in the ligands and their metal chelates may be assigned to azomethine C-H stretching vibration¹⁰.

The spectra in the region 1100 cm⁻¹ and below are much more complicated due to the presence of phenyl ring, M-O and M-N vibrations. However, the band at 930-945 cm⁻¹ in beryllium chelate is due to metal-ligand stretching^{4,6,47} and bands in the region 800-750 are due to aromatic CH vibrations⁴⁰.

In order to get clearer insight of these ligands and their beryllium chelates, the pmr spectral study has been carried out.

The strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding present in the ligands leads to a very broad and weak hydroxyl absorption near 2700 cm⁻¹ so that the pmr spectra are more informative than ir spectra with respect to the nature of O-H bonding. It has been shown that N-aryl salicylaldimines exist solely in the phenolimine form in non-hydroxylic solvents at normal temperatures^{14,41,42}. Any significant presence of the keto-amine form would split the signal arising from the azomethine proton. No splitting of this signal is observed in the pmr spectra of ligands studied here, nor the aromatic proton signals displaced from its normal position. From these data it is assumed that N-aryl salicylaldimines possess the phenolimine structure. The bonded O-H proton signals are found between 12.1 δ to 13.85 δ for N-aryl salicylaldimines and at 8.18 δ and 9.95 δ for salicylaldoxime^{4,9}. This assignment has been verified by deuterium exchange. In ligands, the sharp singlet of azomethine proton is found between 8.18 δ to 9.2 δ . The signals due to -CH₃ protons in N-*p*-tolyl and N-*p*-anisylsalicylaldimines and their beryllium chelates are found at 2.34 δ , 2.53 δ , 3.80 δ and 3.93 δ respectively. The ring protons of aldehyde and aniline appear in the region between 6.5 δ -8.33 δ . In the pmr spectrum of N-*o*-hydroxyphenylsalicylaldimine two signals are found at 13.35 δ and 8.30 δ . The signal at 8.30 δ is assigned to *o*-hydroxy proton of aniline, whereas the 13.35 δ signal is assigned to hydrogen bonded aldehyde O-H proton, both disappear on deuteration. In the pmr spectra of all the beryllium chelates, the signal at 12 δ to 13.85 δ due to phenolic OH proton is absent indicating the participation of the O-H in chelate formation. The signals due to ring protons, azomethine proton and others show no change in their position, but in case of beryllium chelate of N-*o*-hydroxyphenylsalicylaldimine two signals for azomethine CH-proton are found at 8.40 δ and 9.03 δ . In the pmr spectrum of *bis*-(N-*o*-hydroxyphenylsalicylaldimine) beryllium(II) (recorded in DMSO), two broad signals at 13.85 δ and 9.70 δ were found. This is presumably due to presence of hydrogen bonded protons as found in salicylaldoxime complexes.

In the spectrum of *bis*(salicylaldiminato) beryllium(II) (Fig. 2) a doublet is found at 9.97 δ (J=13 Hz) due to N-H protons. This is confirmed by the disappearance of these signals on deuteration. Furthermore, the presence of the doublet also indicates that the two N-H protons are coupled with CH proton of azomethine group. The signal due to CH proton also appears as a doublet at 8.47 δ (J=13 Hz) which is due to coupling between CH and N-H protons. This doublet collapses into a singlet on deuteration.

The beryllium complex of salicylaldoxime also shows two signals at 10.13 δ and 11.30 δ , both disappearing on deuteration. These signals may be due to hydrogen bonded OH. The above data supports

Fig. 2. PMR Spectrum of Bis(N-Salicylaldiminato)beryllium(II) in Dry DMSO.

the conclusion drawn from the ir studies on these ligands and their beryllium chelates.

The mass spectra of the ligands show base peak at m/e 197, 211, 227, 231, 241, 212, 241 for N-phenyl, N-*p*-tolyl, N-*p*-anisyl, N-*p*-chlorophenyl, N-*p*-nitrophenyl, N-*o*-hydroxyphenyl and N-*o*-carboxyphenylsalicylaldimines which are also the molecular ion peaks. The high intensity of the molecular ion peaks is in accordance with the stabilization of the molecule by strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding. Similarly the high resistance of the ligand to hydrolysis reflects the stabilization of the azomethine bond by means of the hydrogen bonded ring system. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that a strong peak at m/e 120 can be assigned to the fragment shown below. This usually occurs with hydrogen transfer resulting in a cluster of peaks at m/e 121, 120, 119. The formation of such stable

heterocyclic species is characteristic of the mass spectra of ortho substituted aromatic Schiff bases^{44,45}. The spectra of N-*p*-tolyl, N-*p*-anisyl, N-*p*-chloro ligands show loss of the *p*-substituted groups resulting in metastable ions. Similarly, the spectra of N-*o*-hydroxyphenyl and N-*o*-carboxyphenylsalicylaldimines show loss of water and carbon dioxide from molecular ion. Another characteristic feature of these Schiff bases is the formation of a species of m/e 168-169. The formation of such a fragment may be due to the loss of CO and the *p*-substituent with proton transfer.

Apart from these major peaks, these spectra also show a peak at m/e 77 corresponding to $C_6H_8^+$ ion formed by the breakdown of the parent ion. These

spectra show that fission at the ring nitrogen bond is more facile than at the ring carbon-bond. The mass spectra of para substituted Schiff bases show essentially the same features, sometimes complicated by the effect of substituents.

It is concluded from the above studies that beryllium forms strong bonds with oxygen and nitrogen containing ligands. It was found that the beryllium complex has the same stability as copper complexes which contradicts the apparent belief that beryllium bonds weakly with ligands containing nitrogen donor atoms⁴⁶. It is also found that N-aryl salicylaldimine beryllium complexes are as stable as the N-alkyl salicylaldimine complexes. The tridentate dibasic ligand, N-*o*-hydroxyphenylsalicylaldimine acts as a monobasic, bidentate ligand towards beryllium, where the amino -OH group takes part only in hydrogen bonding as is found in case of salicylaldoxime. It is interesting to note that N-*o*-carboxyphenylsalicylaldimine acts as a dibasic ligand with beryllium.

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